

A Synthesis of 2:3-Methylenedioxy-11:12-dimethoxy-tetrahydroprotoberberine, an Isomer of Tetrahydroberberine and a Synthesis of 2:3:11:12-Tetramethoxytetrahydroprotoberberine, an Isomer of Tetrahydropalmatine.

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Berberine can be readily degraded to ψ -opianic acid through berberal (Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1890, 57, 1002, Perkin and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1910, 97, 321). It was, therefore, thought that it would be a matter of interest to synthesise an isomer of berberine by substituting ψ -opianic acid in place of opianic acid in the Perkin, Rây and Robinson synthesis of berberine (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 740), and compare the properties of the two alkaloids. The tetrahydro derivative of this isomer should have the constitution (II) as shown below :

ψ -Opianic acid being not yet readily available, this substance which may be called 2:3-methylene-dioxy-11:12:-dimethoxytetrahydroprotoberberine was synthesised in the following manner.

o-Veratraldehyde was condensed with hippuric acid and the α -lactone hydrolysed to benzoic acid and 2:3-dimethoxyphenylpyruvic acid; the latter was then oxidised by hydrogen peroxide to 2:3-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid, which was condensed with β -piperonylethylamine and the 2:3-dimethoxyphenylaceto- β -piperonylethylamide (III) so obtained was converted in a yield of over 80% into a syrupy base. This base which is probably 6:7-methylenedioxy-1-(2:3-methoxybenzyl)-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline (IV) oxidizes rapidly on exposure to air and is readily reduced by zinc and sulphuric acid to 6:7-methylenedioxy-1-(2:3-methoxybenzyl)-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroisoquinoline (V), an oily base yielding a crystalline hydrochloride and picrate. Ring-closure of the formyl derivative was effected in the usual manner with phosphorus oxychloride and 2:3-methylenedioxy-11:12-dimethoxydihydroprotoberberine (VI) thus obtained, was immediately reduced to 2:3-methylenedioxy-11:12-dimethoxytetrahydroprotoberberine (II).

(III)

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

It would be obvious from the formula (V) that ring-closure can take place only in one direction and the dihydroprotoberberine must have the formula (VI).

2:3-Methylenedioxy-11:12-dimethoxytetrahydroprotoberberine (II) is a colourless crystalline base, m.p. 127°. When it is oxidised with iodine in alcoholic solution, it yields 2:3-methylenedioxy-11:12-dimethoxyprotoberberinium iodide (VII) from which the corresponding chloride was prepared. The chloride is decomposed in the usual manner by potassium hydroxide giving 2:3-methylenedioxy-11:12-dimethyl-oxyprotoberberine (VIII) and dimethoxydihydroprotoberberine (VI) which are readily separated as the former is insoluble and the latter soluble in dilute mineral acids.

Next 2:3:11:12-tetramethoxytetrahydroprotoberberine (IX), an isomer of tetrahydropalmatine was synthesised by a method similar to that outlined above in the case of (II). 2:3-Dimethoxyphenylacetic acid condenses with β -veratrylethylamine to yield 2:3-dimethoxyphenylaceto- β -veratrylethylamide (as III) which was converted first

into the dihydroisoquinoline (as IV), and then the latter reduced to 6:7-dimethoxy-1-(2:3-dimethoxybenzyl)-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroisoquinoline (as V), an oily base yielding crystalline salts. Ring-closure of the formyl derivative was effected in the usual manner with phosphorus oxychloride and 2:3:11:12-tetramethoxydihydroprotoberberine (as VI) thus obtained was immediately reduced to 2:3:11:12-tetramethoxytetrahydroprotoberberine (IX).

EXPERIMENTAL.

2:3-Dimethoxyphenylacetic acid.—This acid had been previously prepared from 2:3-dimethoxyphenylmandelonitrile (Heinrich and Krannichfeldt, *Ber.*, 1913, 46, 4023). This acid is more conveniently prepared in the following manner.

o-Veratraldehyde was condensed with the hippuric acid in the presence of acetic anhydride and sodium acetate. The azlactone, m.p. 170° thus obtained was hydrolysed by means of 10% sodium hydroxide solution and the alkaline solution was then saturated with sulphur dioxide, the benzoic acid collected and the filtrate acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid and boiled to decompose the bisulphite compound of the pyruvic acid, when 2:3-dimethoxyphenylpyruvic acid gradually separated in small needles, m.p. 145°. It was oxidised in cold alkaline solution with hydrogen peroxide. On acidifying the solution 2:3-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid, m.p. 84°, separated in an excellent yield. It crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 70-80°) in long beautiful needles.

2:3-Dimethoxyphenylaceto-β-piperonylethylamide.—Equivalent quantities of β-piperonylethylamine¹ and 2:3-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid were heated at 180° for 2 hours. On crystallising the product from benzene, 2:3-dimethoxyphenylaceto-β-piperonylethylamide was obtained in colourless needles in a good yield, m.p. 108° (Found: C, 66.2; H, 6.0. C₁₉H₂₁O₅N requires C, 66.5; H, 6.1 per cent).

6:7-Methylenedioxy-1-(2':3'-dimethoxybenzyl)-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroisoquinoline.—The amide (10 g.) was heated with phosphorus oxychloride (25 c.c.) for 2 hours on the steam-bath and then kept overnight. The mixture was decomposed with cold water and the clear solution thus obtained was made alkaline in the presence of benzene in a separating funnel, the precipitate formed being immediately shaken up with benzene. The alkaline solution was once

more extracted with benzene. The benzene extract was again extracted with dilute sulphuric acid and the acid solution was reduced with zinc dust by heating on the steam-bath for 2 hours till the yellow colour disappeared. The solution was filtered hot and decomposed by means of ammonia and the tetrahydro base extracted with benzene, dried over potassium carbonate and the solvent removed, leaving the base as an oil. The hydrochloride, obtained by dissolving the oil in hot dilute hydrochloric acid and cooling, separated in small clusters of needles, m. p. 160° . (Found: C, 62.5 ; H, 6.2. $C_{19}H_{23}O_4NCl$ requires C, 62.7 ; H, 6.1 per cent).

2 : 3-Methylenedioxy-11:12-dimethoxytetrahydroprotoberberine was obtained in 50% yield by the following method. The tetrahydroisoquinoline was heated with equivalent amount of anhydrous formic acid in an oil-bath at 200° for 2 hours. The product was dissolved in toluene and boiled with phosphorus oxychloride for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. After remaining overnight, light petroleum was added and the clear liquid decanted from the dark coloured gum, the latter extracted with dilute hydrochloric acid (charcoal) and the solution of dihydroprotoberberine reduced by heating with excess of zinc dust for 2 hours, during which the yellow solution became colourless. The hot liquid was filtered, the filtrate decomposed with ammonia, the base extracted with chloroform, dried over potassium carbonate, the chloroform removed and the residue crystallised from methyl alcohol. On recrystallisation from methyl alcohol (charcoal) the substance was obtained in beautiful needles, m. p. 127° . (Found : C, 70.5 ; H, 6.4. $C_{20}H_{21}O_4N$ requires C, 70.8 ; H, 6.2 per cent).

2:3-Methylenedioxy-11:12-dimethoxyprotoberberinium iodide.— 2:3-Methylenedioxy-11:12-dimethoxytetrahydroprotoberberine (1.5 g.) dissolved in alcohol (50 c. c.) containing anhydrous sodium acetate (4 g.) was heated to boiling and a 2% alcoholic solution of iodine (150 c. c.) added slowly, when the periodide separated. After boiling for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, the whole was cooled and the crystals collected, suspended in boiling water and SO_2 was passed, when the iodide separated in yellow needles, m. p. 252° .

2 : 3-Methylenedioxy-11:12-dimethoxyprotoberberinium chloride was obtained by boiling an aqueous suspension of the iodide with excess of freshly precipitated silver chloride for 3 hours on the steam-bath. The filtrate was concentrated and treated with hydrochloric acid, when the chloride separated as yellow needles, m. p. 220° .

Oxy-2:3-methylenedioxy-11:12-dimethoxyprotoberberine.—A hot solution of the chloride (1.5 g) in water (15 c.c.) was added to a hot solution of KOH (6 g.) in water (25 c.c.) and the whole heated on the steam-bath for 3 hours. The yellow mass which separated was collected and extracted many times with boiling dilute hydrochloric acid. The insoluble residue crystallised from glacial acetic acid containing an equal volume of water as light yellow needles, m. p. 230-31°. (Found: C, 68.1; H, 5.0. $C_{20}H_{17}O_5N$ requires C, 68.4; H, 4.8 per cent).

On basifying the hydrochloric acid extract, the dihydroprotoberberine was precipitated. This substance is being further examined.

2:3-Dimethoxyphenylaceto- β -veratrylethylamide was prepared by heating together equivalent quantities of 2:3-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid and β -veratrylethylamine in an oil-bath at 180° for 2 hours. The product crystallised from benzene in colourless needles, m. p. 131°. (Found: C, 66.8; H, 7.0. $C_{20}H_{25}O_5N$ requires C, 66.9; H, 6.9 per cent).

6:7-Dimethoxy-1-(2':3'-dimethoxybenzyl)-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroisoquinoline.—The amide (10 g) was heated with phosphorus oxychloride (25 c.c.) for 2 hours on the steam-bath and then kept overnight. The mixture was worked up in the same manner as in the previous case. The tetrahydro base was obtained as an oil which gave a crystalline hydrochloride, m. p. 204°, separating from dilute HCl in nodules. (Found: C, 63.6; H, 7.5. $C_{20}H_{26}O_4NCl$ requires C, 63.2; H, 7.3 per cent).

2:3:11:12-Tetramethoxytetrahydroprotoberberine.—(i) The tetrahydroisoquinoline was condensed in the presence of sodium bicarbonate with formaldehyde in methyl alcoholic solution. The condensation product which separated as a gum on the addition of water and some salt, was dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid and heated on the steam-bath for a few minutes. The acid solution gave with ammonia a base which crystallised from methyl alcohol in beautiful prisms, m. p. 163°.

(ii) This base was obtained in a better yield by the following method. The tetrahydroisoquinoline was heated with an equivalent amount of anhydrous formic acid in an oil-bath at 200° until effervescence had ceased (2 hours). The product was dissolved in toluene and boiled with phosphorus oxychloride for 1½ hours. After remaining overnight, light petroleum was added and the clear liquid decanted from the dark coloured gum, the latter extracted with dilute

hydrochloric acid (charcoal) and the solution of dihydroprotoberberine reduced by heating with excess of zinc dust for 2 hours on the steam-bath, when the yellow solution became colourless. The hot liquid was filtered and the filtrate decomposed with ammonia, the base extracted with chloroform, dried over potassium carbonate, the chloroform removed and the residue crystallised from methyl alcohol. On recrystallisation from methyl alcohol, the substance was obtained in beautiful prisms, m. p. 163°. The mixed melting point of the products obtained by the two methods remained undepressed. (Found: C, 70.8 ; H, 7.1. $C_{21}H_{25}O_4N$ requires C, 71.0 ; H, 7.0 per cent).

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Received October 23, 1933.

